

DESIGN AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MICROBALLOON- ALUMINUM COMPOSITE-CORE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Novel structural sandwich composites, incorporating syntactic metal foam cores between stiff metallic or composite facesheets, were designed, fabricated, and tested. In this investigation, a foam core laminate, i.e., a core consisting of alumina microballoons in an aluminum matrix and steel face sheets, was prepared using a single step casting process. Mechanical property tests were conducted to verify the correlation between measured and predicted properties. Specific details of design, mechanical properties, and failure behavior of microballoon-aluminum composite core with steel facesheet laminates are presented here.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Conventional structural sandwich composites consist of a lightweight core between two thin facesheets of stiff metallic or composite materials. Sandwich structures are used in applications requiring high stiffness to weight ratios because for a given weight, the sandwich structure has a much higher moment of inertia compared to solid or I-beam structures. In each sandwich structure, the facesheets resist all of the applied edgewise (in-plane) loads and flatwise bending moments, and the core provides most of the shear rigidity. This sandwich core is usually constructed from a honeycomb structure, an open cell organic or ceramic foam, or a closed cell syntactic (organic) foam.

Analogous to the syntactic organic foam concept, syntactic metal foams, incorporating hollow ceramic spheres, i.e., microballoons (mb) in a metal matrix, have been developed [1-4] to increase high specific compressive strength, impact resistance, damage tolerance, and acoustic attenuation. Typical examples of syntactic metal foams include alumina (Al_2O_3) microballoons in aluminum (Al) matrix or alumina microballoons in a matrix of particulate silicon carbide reinforced Al composite (SiC_p/Al). Although syntactic metal foams exhibit attractive material properties, their flexural strength and stiffness are often low for most structural applications. Therefore, a novel structural sandwich composite, consisting of a syntactic metal foam core sandwiched between metallic, ceramic, and composite facesheets, has been developed for structural platforms, armors, hulls, and equipment enclosures for submerged vehicles.

Several sandwich structures with ceramic, composite, and metallic facesheets and syntactic metal foam (e.g., mb/Al or mb/ SiC_p/Al) cores have been fabricated. Facesheet materials included alumina, carbon fiber reinforced aluminum, titanium, high strength steel, SiC_p/Al , and Al. In each case the facesheet was integrally bonded to the metal foam core using a single step casting process. This paper

describes the design, mechanical properties, and failure behavior of (alumina) mb/Al matrix composite core with steel facesheet laminates, hereafter referred to as steel/(mb/Al)/steel. Results of this study indicate that the measured tensile, compressive, and flexural properties are consistent with the predicted behavior.

2.0 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A near net shape casting technique was used to fabricate steel/(mb/Al)/steel laminate rods, plates, and cylinders. During this one step casting process the molten aluminum forms an integral bond with the steel facesheet. Figure 1 shows a cast plate laminate prepared from 2 mm thick, 4340 steel facesheets, A201 aluminum matrix alloy, and Al_2O_3 microballoons (2.5 mm diameter and 0.09 mm wall thickness). Alumina microballoons of uniform wall thickness to diameter (t/d) ratio were provided by Ceramic Filler Inc, Atlanta, Georgia. Typical dimensions of the cast plate were: 15 mm x 120 mm x 200 mm. Water jet cutting was used to prepare several specimens for microstructural evaluation and mechanical property tests. Each as-cast plate was examined by using the conventional ultrasonic C-Scan technique to examine defects such as voids and disbonds at the core/facesheet interface. The ultrasonic technique could not be used for examining any casting defects in the core, because the transmitted signal was strongly attenuated by the microballoons.

Figure 1 Syntactic Metal Foam (mb/Al) Core Laminates with Steel Facesheets: a) Integrally Cast Plate; b) Schematic

A few of the sectioned specimens were also examined by C-Mode Scanning Acoustic Microscope (C-SAM) to detect disbonds at both the core/facesheet and the microballoon/matrix interfaces. The C-SAM examination was conducted at Sonoscan, Inc, Bensonville, Illinois, by generating a 13 mm x 13 mm focused spot on the test specimen with an acoustic lens assembly at frequencies between 30 and 100 MHz.

Optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy were used to characterize the matrix microstructure, and to examine defects such as microcracks, voids, and disbonds in the core and at the core-facesheet interface.

Mechanical property tests of the foam core laminate specimens were performed according to the ASTM Standards conventionally used for sandwich constructions. These tests are listed below.

Flatwise Compression	ASTM C-365
Edgewise Compression	ASTM E-9
Flexure Test	ASTM C-393
Flatwise Tension	ASTM C-297
Edgewise Tension	ASTM E-8

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Design Development

Ceramic microballoons were incorporated in the aluminum matrix to produce mb/Al as a new family of metal matrix composites [1-4]. Using microballoons of different sizes and t/d ratios in the aluminum [1-3] and SiC_p/Al [5] matrices, syntactic metal foams were successfully produced by the casting process. These composites exhibited low density, moderate compressive strength, high impact energy absorption, and stress/strain response similar to the syntactic foams [3, 5]. Table 1 lists the compressive strengths of several as-cast syntactic metal foams. These results indicate the effect of microballoon size, matrix composition and reinforcement loading on the compressive strength of the composite as follows:

Table 1 Compressive Strength of As - Cast mb/Al Syntactic Foams (Nominal 55 v/o)

		Compressive Strength, MPa (Specific Compressive Strength, MPa/gm/cm ³)				
		2300 μ m	1000 μ m	250 μ m	60 μ m	Unreinforced
Al Matrix	mb Size					
	A356	---	210 (83)	396 (145)	---	110 (40.7)
	A201	210 (105)	289 (114)	413 (151)	448 (155)	241 (87)
	15 v/o SiC _p /A356 Al	---	354 (140)	---	---	221 (76)

- Average specific compressive strength increases with reduced mb size
- Modulus is nearly independent of mb size
- Microballoon reinforced matrix exhibits higher specific strength (i.e., strength/density) than unreinforced matrix
- Specific compressive strength increases with higher strength matrix (e.g., SiC_p/Al and A201 compared to A356 aluminum alloy)

Syntactic metal foams offer high specific compressive strength and high acoustic attenuation characteristics, but their bending stiffness and bending strengths are low. Therefore a sandwich construction design was introduced where mb/Al foam becomes the light weight core between stiff facesheet materials. With improved stiffness and strength, these mb/Al foam core laminates are then candidate materials for structural components that are conventionally fabricated from thick metallic plates or solid I-beams.

The mb/Al core laminates were developed using the basic design principles and conditions involved in designing the structural sandwich composites and these conditions are shown below.

- 1) Laminate facesheets should be strong enough to withstand the tensile and compressive stresses imposed by the design loads, and thick enough to prevent failure at the core/facesheet interface.

- 2) The core should be thick enough and have sufficient rigidity and strength to prevent overall buckling, shear crimping, face wrinkling, and intercell dimpling when the sandwich structure is loaded in edgewise compression.
- 3) The core/facesheet interface bonding must be strong enough to withstand flatwise tensile and shear stresses induced by the load.

Based on these design considerations, steel facesheet thickness was determined as a function of the thickness of the mb/Al core. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the stress state during the bending conditions. Failure of the laminate is governed by the tensile stress experienced by the core as the core has lower strength in tension than in compression. Assuming an average tensile strength of 200 MPa for 55 volume percent (v/o) mb/A201 Al foam core, the minimum steel facesheet thickness was determined.

Figure 2 Stress Diagram Resulting From Bending Moment (M) Applied to a Laminate Composed of a mb/Al Core (A) and Two Steel Facesheets (B)

Figure 2 defines the facing and core stress state:

$$\frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_b} = \left(\frac{E_a}{E_b} \right) \frac{a}{b}$$

using: Elastic modulus of mb/Al core, $E_a = 31$ GPa,

Elastic modulus of steel facesheet, $E_b = 200$ GPa,

Tensile stress in mb/Al core, σ_a , @ core/facesheet interface = 200 MPa, and

Maximum tensile stress in outer fibers of facesheet, $\sigma_b = 1860$ MPa

$$\frac{a}{b} = 0.694$$

If the core thickness, $2a = 1.00$ cm

Laminate thickness $2b = 1.44$ cm

i.e., facing thickness $(b-a) \geq 0.22$ cm (0.087-in.)

Based on this design several steel // (mb/Al) // steel plates were integrally cast and subsequently evaluated for laminate integrity and material properties.

3.2 Material Evaluation

Ultrasonic c-scans of as-cast plates revealed a good metallurgical bond at the core/facesheet interface and no major disbonds or defects. These results suggest that the processing conditions were adequate to provide reproducible castings of good quality. Furthermore, Figure 3 shows a C-SAM image of the transverse section of the laminate that indicates uniform distribution of microballoons, a continuous matrix with no microcracks, and good bonding at both the facesheet/matrix and microballoon/matrix interfaces. Optical microscopy examination of several specimens confirmed the uniform mb distribution in the matrix and an intimate mechanical contact (bond) between the mb and the aluminum matrix. As shown in Figure 4, aluminum matrix has completely infiltrated into the narrow spaces between the microballoons and between the microballoons and the facesheets. In each cast plate, the conforming aluminum layer adjacent to the steel facesheet revealed (Figures 3 and 4a) good metallurgical bonds at the core/facesheet interface.

Figure 3 Ultrasonic C-SAM Image of the Transverse Section of the Steel/(mb/Al)/Steel Sandwich Showing Uniform Distribution of Microballoons, and No Disbonds at Core/Facesheet Interface

Figure 4 Photomicrograph Showing Aluminum Matrix Infiltration Into the Narrow Spaces Between Microballoons a) Steel/(mb/Al)/Steel Laminate; b) Dendritic Structure near mb/Matrix Interface

3.3 Mechanical Properties

Tension, compression and flexure tests were conducted to determine the mechanical properties of the steel / (mb/Al) // steel laminate, and also to examine the failure behavior of the constituent core materials and associated interfaces. During flatwise compression, the stress-strain response (Fig. 5) is governed by the deformation behavior of the core. Like elastic-brittle closed cell foams (Ref 6), the mb/Al core shows linear elasticity to a compressive stress value of approximately 220 MPa, followed by a collapse of the cellular core structure to a plateau at reduced stress levels (Fig.5). Modulus is determined by the initial slope of the stress-strain curve. This linear elastic region is associated with elastic deformation of the cell walls (matrix ligaments) as shown schematically in Figure 5. The plateau region at the stress level 130 ± 25 MPa, is associated with the collapse of the cell walls. After the cell walls have completely collapsed and further strain compresses the solid, the composite exhibits increase in strength with increasing strain.

Figure 5 Stress Strain Response of Steel // (mb/Al) // Steel Laminate During Flatwise Compression Test . Also Shown is the Schematic of mb/Al Core During Deformation : (a) Elastic Deformation of Cell Walls; (b) Collapse of Cell Walls (Note: The Cell Wall is Merely a Representation of a Region and not Part of the Actual Core)

During edgewise compression and tension tests, modulus and strength values are governed by the cross sectional area of the steel facesheet normal to the applied load. Each laminate specimen exhibited the linear stress strain curve up to 95% of the overall deformation. Measured modulus, yield strength, and ultimate strength values were consistent with predicted values given the assumption that the steel facesheets constitute 30% of the area, and bear approximately 95 to 100% of the applied load (Table 2).

Table 2 Mechanical Property Test Data of Steel// (mb/Al)// Steel Laminates (Density 3.7 g/cm³)

Test	Modulus GPa	Yield Strength MPa	Ultimate Strength MPa	Comments
Flatwise Compression 	31	---	220	Stress-Strain response Similar to Syntactic Foam
Edgewise Compression 	54	540	595	Load Borne Primarily by Facesheet
Flatwise Tension	---	---	22	Core Failure Along Highest mb Packing path
Edgewise Tension	82	550	580	Load Borne Primarily by Facesheet

As a consequence of machining, each tension and compression specimen had either two (edgewise) or four (flatwise) sides which exposed partially cut microballoons at the core surface. The cut mb cavities act as high stress-concentrators, as well as reduce the load carrying capabilities of the exposed cell walls. In these mechanical tests, specimens with an exposed machined core face will have lower strength as compared to a core where all the microballoons are completely encapsulated within aluminum matrix.

Flatwise tension tests were used to evaluate the core/facesheet interface bond strength, as opposed to evaluating the core tensile strength. Results from these tests indicated that each specimen failed in the core and the core/facesheet interface bond remained intact. This suggested that core/facesheet interface bond strength was greater than the measured flatwise tensile strength value of 24 MPa. A critical examination of the failure surface revealed the following two features: 1) failure initiated from the failure of outer ligaments exposed to high stress-concentrations, and (2) propagated along the surface consisting of highest packaging density of microballoons.

During the 3-point bend (flexure) test, steel facesheets experienced up to 1800 MPa with an average core strength of 52 MPa, prior to laminate failure. Facesheet stress was consistent with the predicted stress value of 1860 MPa. The core failure was associated with a shear crack propagating at about 45° to the neutral axis.

Since the results from tension, compression, and bend tests, indicated good correlation between measured and predicted properties, this validated the design methodology for foam core laminates. In addition, several mechanical property tests of other foam core laminates (Ti//mb/Al//Ti and SiC_p/Al//mb/Al//SiC_p/Al) have also confirmed good correlation between measured and predicted properties.

4.0 SUMMARY

Novel structural sandwich composites incorporating syntactic metal foam cores between stiff metallic or composite facesheets, were designed, fabricated, and tested. In this investigation, flat plates of the foam core laminate, i.e., steel // (alumina)mb/Al // steel, were produced in a single step casting process. From the cast laminates, test specimens were prepared to verify the correlation between measured and predicted tensile, compressive, and flexural properties. Results of mechanical property tests indicated good correlation between the measured and predicted properties. Flatwise tension and compression specimen exhibited stress-strain behavior similar to closed cell foams. The edgewise tensile and edgewise compressive responses were governed by the mechanical properties of facesheets.

Based on these results, syntactic metal foam core laminates are concluded to exhibit low density, moderate stiffness, and high compressive strength. In addition, these laminates have the potential of high impact resistance and high acoustic attenuation characteristics. By selecting the appropriate constituent materials for the syntactic metal foams and stiff facesheets, the foam core laminates can be tailored to satisfy the requirements of specific structural applications and replace thick plate designs.

5.0 REFERENCES

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